

Leveraging Generative AI for Translanguaging Support in Computational Thinking Education: A Work in Progress

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ABSTRACT

This research-in-progress investigates how generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) can be leveraged to integrate translanguaging strategies into an upper elementary computational thinking (CT) curriculum, supporting multilingual students' learning and CS identity development. Through a Research-Practice Partnership (RPP), this study explores the integration of translanguaging into computational thinking and fractions instruction using GenAI tools to enhance student engagement and understanding. Utilizing a design-based implementation research (DBIR) approach, we will conduct a three-phase study involving curriculum adaptation, iterative refinement, and impact evaluation. Findings from this study will inform translanguaging pedagogies in STEM education and the responsible use of AI in linguistically diverse classrooms.

KEYWORDS

Computational thinking; generative AI; translanguaging; multilingual education; computer science education

INTRODUCTION

The integration of computational thinking (CT) and computer science (CS) education into K–12 classrooms has gained momentum over the past decade. However, multilingual students, particularly Latine English Learners (ELs), continue to face systemic barriers to participation in CS education, including linguistic and pedagogical obstacles that hinder engagement and learning outcomes (Estrada et al., 2020). This research-in-progress investigates how GenAI can be leveraged to integrate translanguaging strategies into an upper elementary CT curriculum to support multilingual students' learning and CS identity development.

Our work builds upon an established RPP among Digital Promise and participating school districts that have worked to broaden participation in CS education, particularly among Latine ELs, whose enrollment in CS courses has remained disproportionately low (Estrada et al., 2020). Given that translanguaging supports multilingual students' development of CT and literacy skills, as well as other STEM disciplines such as math and science (García & Lin, 2017; Moschkovich, 2013; Suarez, 2021), this study seeks to integrate translanguaging practices into a computational thinking curriculum for grades 3-5, augmented with GenAI support (Estrada et al., 2020).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This research is grounded in three key theoretical perspectives. **Translanguaging pedagogy** frames our approach to supporting multilingual learners by recognizing their entire linguistic repertoire as a resource rather than a barrier to learning (García & Lin, 2017; Orellana & García, 2014). Translanguaging involves blending multiple communicative modes, including language, gestures, and symbols, to make meaning, thus facilitating both language and content learning (Wei, 2018). Research demonstrates that translanguaging can improve multilingual students' engagement and sense of belonging in STEM learning environments by allowing them to express ideas in both their home language and the language of instruction (Suarez, 2021). Additionally, translanguaging aligns with five empirically supported teaching practices for engaging multilingual students in STEM, including the use of disciplinary practices, classroom discourse, and multimodal resources (Lee et al., 2020).

Computational thinking education provides another key foundation for this research. CT involves problem-solving processes such as decomposition, abstraction, pattern recognition, and algorithmic thinking (Wing,

2006). In K–8 education, CT is often integrated into subject areas. For example, mathematics instruction, where concepts such as sequencing and conditionals can support proportional reasoning and numerical problem-solving (Wilkerson & Fenwick, 2017; Weintrop et al., 2016). Subject-area curriculum introduces CT concepts through a series of coding and non-coding activities designed to reinforce disciplinary understanding. By embedding translanguaging strategies into integrated CT and disciplinary subjects, we seek to create a more equitable learning environment for multilingual learners.

The third perspective is **AI-augmented learning**, which explores the role of GenAI in enhancing multilingual and STEM education. GenAI tools, such as ChatGPT, can provide personalized language support by generating multilingual explanations, culturally relevant coding problems, and multimodal learning experiences (Li et al., 2022). These affordances align with research demonstrating that AI-driven tools can scaffold language learning and computational literacy for multilingual students (García & Lin, 2017; Moschkovich, 2013). However, concerns about AI bias, misinformation, and ethical use must also be addressed, particularly in the context of underrepresented student populations (Bender et al., 2021; Gebru et al., 2021; Noble, 2018).

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This study employs a **design-based implementation research (DBIR)** approach to iteratively refine instructional strategies and assess their effectiveness in real-world classroom settings (Penuel et al., 2011). The research will be conducted in three phases. In the first phase, an existing grade 3-5 computational thinking curriculum will be adapted in collaboration with district educators to integrate GenAI-facilitated translanguaging strategies and piloted in third- to fifth-grade classrooms. Teachers will participate in professional development on translanguaging, AI integration, and culturally responsive CT instruction. Data collection will include teacher interviews, classroom observations, student assessments, and reflections to analyze implementation strategies and student engagement. The second phase will refine instructional strategies and expand implementation to additional classrooms while assessing the evolving role of GenAI in supporting translanguaging and CT learning. Data collection will include student assessments, teacher self-efficacy surveys, classroom artifacts, and additional interviews, with iterative feedback cycles guiding improvements. In the final phase, the effectiveness of GenAI-supported translanguaging strategies will be evaluated through a comparative study of student learning outcomes in treatment and comparison classrooms. The analysis will examine student engagement, computational thinking skill development, and socioemotional outcomes. Findings will be disseminated to educational stakeholders to inform broader adoption and policy recommendations.

Measures

A combination of quantitative and qualitative measures will be used to assess the impact of the GenAI-supported translanguaging strategies on students' computational thinking development, engagement, and learning experiences.

Quantitative Measures

Computational Thinking Assessments: Students' computational thinking (CT) skills will be assessed using the *Assessment of Computing for Elementary Students (ACES)* (Brennan & Resnick, 2012). ACES is a validated instrument that measures students' understanding of key CT concepts, including loops, conditionals, and debugging. Pre- and post-intervention assessments will be conducted to evaluate changes in students' CT proficiency over the course of the study.

Student Attitude Survey: The *Elementary Student Coding Attitudes Survey (ESCAS)* (Werner et al., 2019) will be administered to assess students' confidence and interest in coding and computational thinking. This survey includes Likert-scale items that capture students' perceptions of their abilities, engagement, and attitudes toward learning CT concepts. The pre- and post-surveys will provide insights into how the intervention influences students' self-efficacy and motivation.

District Math and Language Scores: Standardized assessment data in mathematics and language arts will be analyzed to examine broader trends in student performance. These district-provided scores will allow researchers to explore potential correlations between participation in the GenAI-supported translanguaging curriculum and improvements in students' overall academic achievement.

Teacher Surveys: Surveys will be conducted with participating teachers to document instructional strategies, implementation challenges, and perceptions of GenAI tools (Estrada et al., 2020). Surveys will include both Likert-scale and open-ended questions to capture nuanced perspectives on teaching practices and curriculum adaptation.

Qualitative Measures

Teacher Interviews: Semi-structured interviews will also be conducted with participating teachers to document instructional strategies, implementation challenges, and perceptions of GenAI tools (Estrada et al., 2020). Teachers will reflect on the effectiveness of translanguaging strategies and AI-generated supports in facilitating student learning. Surveys will include both Likert-scale and open-ended questions to capture nuanced perspectives on teaching practices and curriculum adaptation.

Classroom Observations: Researchers will conduct structured classroom observations to document teacher-student interactions, student engagement levels, and the ways in which translanguaging and computational thinking practices are integrated into instruction. Observational protocols will capture key moments of student participation, discourse, and problem-solving, providing qualitative insights into how the intervention functions in practice.

Student Interviews: Four diverse students from each pilot classroom will be selected for pre- and post-intervention interviews to capture their experiences with translanguaging and AI-supported learning (Estrada et al., 2020). These semi-structured interviews will explore students' engagement, understanding of computational thinking concepts, and perceptions of AI-generated support. The interviews will also help assess how translanguaging strategies influence students' confidence and sense of belonging in computational thinking activities.

DATA ANALYSIS PLAN

A combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis techniques will be used to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention. Qualitative data, including teacher and student interviews, classroom observations, and artifacts, will be analyzed using grounded theory coding to identify emergent themes. Quantitative analysis will include statistical modeling to assess trends in student learning outcomes. Specifically, regression analysis will be used to measure the relationship between GenAI-supported translanguaging strategies and students' computational thinking skill development. Propensity score matching will be employed to control for baseline differences between treatment and comparison groups. Additionally, multilevel modeling will be conducted to account for clustering effects within classrooms. Findings from these analyses will provide empirical evidence on the impact of GenAI-integrated translanguaging strategies on multilingual students' computational thinking and coding attitudes.

IMPLICATIONS

This study has the potential to advance knowledge in three key areas. First, it will provide empirical evidence on how translanguaging can be effectively integrated into CT education through GenAI support. Second, it will develop scalable teacher professional development resources that empower educators to use GenAI in translanguaging-infused instruction. Third, it will offer policy and practice recommendations for leveraging AI to support multilingual learners in STEM education.

By integrating GenAI into computational thinking education, this research aims to foster inclusive learning environments that validate and leverage students' cultural and linguistic identities. Through design-based implementation research, we will provide critical insights into the affordances and limitations of GenAI for enhancing translanguaging practices in K-12 education.

GENERATIVE AI USE

We employed generative AI tools for language enhancement and document structuring. We evaluated the output by verifying alignment with research objectives and ensuring accuracy in educational content. The authors assume all responsibility for the content of this submission.

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